

Extraction and Direct Spectrophotometric Estimation of Palladium(II) with Isonitrosobenzoylacetone

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Manuscript received 9 August 1977, revised 3 April 1978, accepted 22 June 1978

A rapid spectrophotometric method based on the extraction of Pd(II) with isonitrosobenzoylacetone in benzene and measurements of the colour in the organic phase at 415 nm, is described in this paper. The proposed method is free from the interference of other noble metals and metals which are usually associated with Pd. 56 μ g of Pd in 10 ml solution could be determined with an accuracy of 3% at 95% confidence limit. The analysis of a silver alloy containing 3.89% Pt, Pd and traces of gold gave a value of $0.097 \pm 0.003\%$ for Pd compared to the reported value of $0.104 \pm 0.004\%$.

ISONITROBENZOYLACETONE (HINBA), which reacts with transition metals ions to form colored complexes^{1,2}, has not been used in the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. The present paper reports a systematic study of the extraction and direct spectrophotometric estimation of trace amounts of Palladium with HINBA.

Experimental

Apparatus: A Pye-UNICAM SP-500 Series-2 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. Radioactivity and pH were measured as described in an earlier communication³.

Reagent: Reagents and chemicals used were of Analar grade. Stock solutions of palladium were prepared and analysed as reported earlier⁴. Solutions for interference study were obtained by dissolving appropriate salts in water to give 10 mg of the element per ml and they were standardised by standard methods⁵. HINBA was synthesised by following the procedure recommended by Wolf⁶. Radioisotopes were supplied by the Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay.

Procedure For Extraction And Spectrophotometric Estimation of Palladium: The extraction of palladium was studied by equilibrating 224 μ g of Pd in 50 ml of aqueous solution with 10 ml of a solution of HINBA in an organic solvent. The two phases were separated and the pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was measured. Pd in each phase was estimated by using isonitrosoacetophenone⁷. Radioisotopes, whenever available, were used to investigate the extraction of other ions. The separation factors were calculated in the usual way³.

For spectrophotometric estimation, 5 ml solution containing 5-150 μ g of Pd was made 1M with respect

to H₂SO₄, keeping the total volume to 10 ml. It was shaken for 5 minutes with 8 ml of 0.1% solution of HINBA in benzene. The organic phase was collected in a 10 ml flask. The aqueous phase was washed with 2 ml of the reagent solution which was added to the solution in the flask. The volume of the solution was made upto the mark, if required, with benzene and its absorbance was measured at 415 nm. The amount of Pd was determined from a calibration curve.

Procedure for the determination of Pd in a silver alloy containing Au, Pd and Pt: 44-200 mg of the alloy were dissolved in 10 ml of 1 : 1 HNO₃ and the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was taken in water and AgBr was precipitated by adding KBr solution. The precipitate was removed by filtration and washed with water. The filtrate and the washings were transferred into a 60-ml separatory funnel, treated with 8 ml of 10% Hg(NO₃)₂ solution, made 1M with respect to H₂SO₄ and extracted thrice with 8 ml of 0.2% HINBA in benzene. The extracts were collected in a 25 ml flask, and made upto the mark with benzene. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 415 nm against reagent blank. The amount of palladium was calculated from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Extraction studies reveal that a benzene solution of HINBA extracts palladium quantitatively from aqueous solutions of pH 0-1.5 and also from 1-8 M H₂SO₄, 1-4 M CH₃COOH and 1-2M HNO₃. The extraction coefficient of Pd is found to be greater than 500. The extraction of palladium is independent of contact time over the period 5-60 minutes. It decreases from 97.0% at pH 2-0 to 56.0% at pH 10.3. Of the solvents investigated, benzene is the

best extractant for Pd. In the pH range 1.2-5.9, HINBA distributes between benzene and 1M NaClO₄ with a constant ratio which is independent of its concentrations. Its partition coefficient value is found to be 4.0±0.1 at 30°±1°. Above pH 5.9, its extraction decreases and it is not extracted into benzene from 1M NaClO₄ solution of pH 10.1. Its acid dissociation constant calculated from extraction data obtained with 1M NaClO₄ is 3.3±0.2×10⁻⁷g mol./litre at 30°±1°.

Pd extracted into 10 ml of benzene with HINBA can be transferred into the aqueous phase by equilibrating the organic extract twice with 5 ml of 0.05M HCl. This occurs possibly due to the formation of chloro-complexes of palladium, which are non-extractable into benzene.

Neutral salts such as nitrates and sulfates of most metal ions do not have significant effect on the extraction of palladium. Cyanide, chloride, bromide, iodide, thiocyanate and EDTA hinder the extraction of palladium into benzene. The separation factors for Cu²⁺, Tl⁺, Ca²⁺, S⁶⁺, Co³⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Ag⁺, Fe³⁺, Zr⁴⁺, K⁺, Ru⁸⁺, Cs⁺, Pt⁴⁺ and Ir⁴⁺ are as high as 10⁶, while those for Ce⁴⁺, W⁶⁺, Sb⁵⁺, Ni²⁺ and Rh³⁺ exceed 10⁵. They are 2.3×10⁴ for Hg²⁺, 5.5×10³ for Au³⁺, 3.3×10³ for Se⁴⁺ and 2.3×10² for Os⁴⁺.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium : The benzene extract of Pd-HINBA complex exhibits a strong absorption maximum at 415 nm., and the reagent solution in benzene shows negligible absorption at this wavelength. Hence, the wavelength 415 nm. was selected for all absorbance measurements. The molar extinction coefficient at the wavelength of maximum absorption is 11,430 mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹, based on the total palladium taken. The color follows Beer's law in the range of 0.5 to 15 µg of Pd per ml and its intensity remains unchanged upto 24 hours. The variation of the reagent concentration from 0.1 to 0.4% does not seem to have significant effect on the color developed with 150 µg of Pd. 10 ml of 0.2% solution of HINBA were employed for the estimation of 5-150 µg of Pd in 50 ml aqueous-acid solution. Table 1 shows that many

ions in 5-100 mg amounts do not cause interference in the spectrophotometric determination of Pd with HINBA.

The interference by Cl⁻, Br⁻, CN⁻ and CNS⁻ can be suppressed by extracting Pd in the presence of excess of mercuric nitrate solution. Cl⁻ and Br⁻ do not interfere, if Palladium is extracted from 1M CH₃COOH. SO₃²⁻ and NO₂⁻ are oxidised by a dilute solution of KMnO₄ prior to the extraction of Pd. EDTA does not interfere, if the extraction is carried out at pH 2.5. However, for quantitative recovery of palladium, three extractions are necessary. The interference due to thiourea is removed by oxidising it with bromine water, removing the excess bromine by boiling and adding Hg(NO₃)₂ solution.

Nature of the extracted species. Job's continuous variation method as adopted by Irving and Pierce⁶ for two phase systems was employed to study the nature of the extracted species. The curves in (Fig 2) obtained with equimolar solutions indicate two

Fig. 1 Job's continuous variation method
 -O-O-O- at 415 nm 4.208 × 10⁻⁴M of each reactant
 -Δ-Δ-Δ- at 415 nm 8.416 × 10⁻⁴m of each reactant
 -●-●-●- at 475 nm 8.416 × 10⁻⁴m of each reactant

maxima at the ratios of Pd : HINBA equal to 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, corresponding to the formation of Pd(INBA)⁺ and Pd(INBA)₂ respectively. The positions of the maxima are independent of concentrations of the reactants and the wavelength of the light employed. It may, therefore, be inferred that the color extracted into benzene in the presence of excess of HINBA is a neutral species Pd(INBA)₂.

Precision, Accuracy and Sensitivity : Solutions of known palladium content and a silver alloy containing known amount of palladium, 3.89% Pt

TABLE - 1 NON-INTERFERING IONS IN THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Pd WITH HINBA. Pd TAKEN=56 µg

Amount in mg.	Ions.
5	Ru(III), Rh(III) and Os(IV)
10	Ca(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Pt(IV), Ir(IV), Zn(II), Cr(III), Ti(IV), Borate, Oxalate, Chloride, Bromide.
15	Al(III), Mo(VI)
20	Pb(III), Cd(II), Sr(II), Ca(II)
50	Urea, citrate, acetate, tartrate, nitrate, persulfate, sulfate.
Large excess	Hg(II), Be(II), Mn(II), Ba(II).

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and traces of Au, were analysed for testing the accuracy and precision of the proposed spectrophotometric method. Ten determinations with 56.0 μg of Pd in 10 ml solution gave an average of 55.6 μg , which varied between 54.4 μg and 56.8 μg at 95% confidence limit. The value for Pd in the silver alloy was found to be $0.097 \pm .003\%$ (4 determinations) which agreed well with the reported value⁹ of 0.104-0.004%. 0.56 μg of Pd in 1 ml solution gave an absorbance of 0.06.

References

1. F. FEIGL, *Oester. Chem. Z-tg*, 1923, 26, 85.
2. V. S. BHAGWAT, S. W. DHAWLE and G. M. PANDIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 53.
3. U. B. TALWAR and B. C. HALDAR, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, 57, 53.
4. U. B. TALWAR and B. C. HALDAR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, 38, 1929.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., London, 1961.
6. L. WOLFF, P. BOCK, G. LORENTZ and P. TRAPPE, *Ann*, 1902, 325, 127.
7. U. B. TALWAR and B. C. HALDAR, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1967, 39, 264.
8. H. R. M. IRVING and T. B. PIERCE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2565.
9. Z. K. DOCTOR and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Radioanal. Chem.* 1969, 3, 405.